

BOARD ATTRIBUTES AND ENVIRONMENTAL SOCIAL AND GOVERNANCE (ESG) DISCLOSURE IN LISTED SERVICE FIRMS IN NIGERIA

ABDULRAZAK MOHAMMED ALIYU¹, AHMAD BUKOLA UTHMAN, PhD² and KEHINDE LAWAL³

¹Department of Accounting, Nile University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria.

²Lecturer Department of Accounting, Nile University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria.

³Department of Accounting, Nile University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria.

Email: ¹abdulattul@gmail.com, ²ahmad.uthman@nileuniversity.edu.ng, ³twinsworld80@gmail.com

ORCID: ¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9613-3893>, ²<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4272-5574>,

³<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-6953-5831>

Abstract

Although there exist increasing stakeholder pressure and focus on environmental, social and governance (ESG) disclosure, among which are regulatory bodies and investors. A number of listed service companies in Nigeria have inconsistent ESG reporting resulting from inadequacies in board procedures meant to address sustainability risks. This study investigates the effect of board attributes on the ESG disclosure of listed service firms in Nigeria, with a population of 45 firms and a sample size of 16, utilizing an ex-post facto research design and multiple regression to analyze data gathered from the financial statements of the sampled firms. This study adopts general least squares and reveals that board size and composition have a negative and significant effect on ESG disclosure, the board corporate social responsibility committee has positive and significant effect, while board gender diversity and board audit committee have an insignificant effect. The strong conviction of the research is that board qualities are crucial factors that influence the ESG performance of the listed service companies in Nigeria. Good governance systems, board diversity, and sustainability control mechanisms increases the sensitivity of the firms towards stakeholders demand and their long-term sustainability. The study recommends, amongst other things, that listed service firm should follow the inclusion of independent, competent, and professionally skilled directors on the board to facilitate objectivity and sustainability focus.

Keywords: Board Attributes, Board Size, Board Composition, Board Gender Diversity, Board Social Responsibility Committee, ESG Disclosure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) issues are no longer on the borders of corporate disclosure but at the core of corporate legitimacy, risk management, and long-term value creation. Those companies that incorporate environmental stewardship, social responsibility, and good governance can mitigate regulatory and reputational risk, raise capital, and enhance operations resilience, the latter of which is more tangible in emerging markets such as Nigeria (Aigienohuwa & Irowa-Omoregie, 2025). Board attributes are very important governance processes where firms are converting their ESG ambitions into practice. The board of directors establishes the tone at the top and controls strategy and resource allocation; thus, board features, such as size, composition, gender diversity, CSR/sustainability committee, and audit committee structures, influence the prioritization of ESG, disclosure quality, and

implementation (Abdulkarim et al., 2023). Board size affects deliberation, monitoring, and decision-making ability. The larger boards can provide a wider range of skills and legitimacy to engage the stakeholders; still, there are coordination issues that can point to accountability (Izomoh et al., 2024). The empirical findings in Nigeria indicate a conflicting impact of the size of the board on company performance, which suggests that size is not a sufficient condition to predict ESG performance without considering the identity of the individuals on the board and its functioning.

Board composition of the board, especially the balance between the executive director, non-executive directors, and independent directors. Independent and expert directors are theorized to strengthen ESG supervision by minimizing agency issues and increasing risk and disclosure supervision. Investigations into the topic of board composition and sustainability reporting in Nigerian listed companies in recent studies underline the significance of independence and expertise in the credible disclosure of ESG (Usman & Yahaya, 2023).

Gender diversity within boards has gained a lot of prominence. Gender diversity is put forward to enrich board deliberations and increase ethical sensitivity and stakeholder orientation, which applies to ESG. Nigerian surveys and empirical research, nevertheless, show that women continue to be under-represented in corporate boards and mixed results on female representation and company performance (Okon et al. Atanda & Anietimfon, 2020; Akpan et al., 2025).

The institutionalization of board concern with social and environmental issues occurs with the presence of a CSR/sustainability committee. These committees are able to focus knowledge, foster disclosure processes, and tie sustainability measures to strategy. The findings of consumer and industrial companies based in Nigeria indicate that the commitment of governance committees to sustainability reporting is more developed but depends on the mandate, the supply of resources, and board support.

The key issues involved in the credibility of ESG-related reporting include audit committees, especially where ESG reporting intersects with financial ramifications (e.g., provisions, contingent liabilities, green investments). Attributes of the audit committee, such as independence and financial experience/financial diligence, therefore affect the relevance and standard of sustainability and financial reporting in listed firms in Nigeria (Obetoh et al., 2024). The audit committees are supported by the regulatory requirements of listed companies in Nigeria.

The field of this research is reflected in the sphere of listed service companies in Nigeria, i.e., the sphere that comprises financial services, ICT services, hospitality, and other service providers listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX).

Listed service firms are reputation-intensive and highly monitored by the investors, and this makes them an ideal environment to examine the relationships between board attributes and ESGs. The database of companies listed on the NGX gives a clear sampling frame to analyze the sectors.

Due to increasing economic development and size of the service sectors, the sectors' activities resulted in significant pressure on the environment, resources and social well-being (Sadiq et al., 2023). Although there is increasing stakeholder pressure and focus on sustainability among the regulatory bodies, a significant number of listed service companies in Nigeria have inconsistent ESG reporting and ambiguity in board procedures to address the sustainability risks (Osongbule, Zubairu, & Naburgi, 2025).

The Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) released a forensic audit report on widely publicized shareholders' dispute in Ikeja Hotel PLC. The report revealed multibillion naira related party transactions involving irregularities (Nwachukwu, 2025). Recently there was growing public outcry by the organized labour in the hospitality sector in Nigeria over worsening employee exploitation in big hotels in the country, as such called on the government to investigate and deal with the issue appropriately (Oyesola, 2025).

To be able to target governance reforms and make them effective, investors and regulators require evidence on how board attributes meaningfully enhance ESG performance. Although previous studies have investigated the attributes of boards, sustainability reporting, or committee effects separately, no sector-specific data (especially service firms) has studied how board size, composition, gender diversity, the presence of board CSR/sustainability committees, and board audit committee attributes jointly affect ESG outcomes.

Additionally, most of the previous studies are from developed countries (China: Yin & Hu, 2025; Ding et al., 2025; Latin America: Pinherio et al., 2024), leaving a geographical gap. In addition, a period gap was also documented as some of the previous studies focused on a period below 2014 (Collevecchio, 2024; Nuhu & Alam, 2024; Wasiuzzaman & Subramaniam, 2023). This study addresses these gaps by investigating board attributes on the ESG in listed service firms in Nigeria from 2014-2024.

This study therefore, hypothesizes that:

- H₀₁: Board size has no significant effect on the ESG of listed service firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₂: Board composition has no significant effect on the ESG of listed service firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₃: Board gender diversity has no significant effect on the ESG of listed service firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₄: Board CSR committee has no significant effect on the ESG of listed service firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₅: Board audit committee has no significant effect on the ESG of listed service firms in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews the related literature, which involves a conceptual framework, a theoretical review, and an empirical review.

Figure 1 below represents the conceptual framework

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) is a set of standards that evaluates the sustainability and the moral implications of a company (Najaf et al., 2024). This paper defines ESG as the incorporation of environmental stewardship (e.g., emissions reduction), social responsibility (e.g., inclusiveness), and governance practices (e.g., transparency) into corporate strategy, which is determined through ESG scores and disclosures. In addition, board attributes include the structural and demographic features of the board that affect ESG oversight, which include board size, board composition, gender diversity, and the existence of a CSR/sustainability committee, all of which amount to governance effectiveness. Board size refers to the total number of directors on a board (Basile et al., 2025). This paper describes it as the quantitative number of members of the board, and it is assumed that the optimal number of board members (7-12 members) improves ESG performance as it provides a balance between expertise and coordination.

Board composition is the percentage of independent directors (Najaf et al., 2024). In this paper, it is argued to be the proportion of non-executive directors, where the greater the level of independence, the greater the ESG monitoring and strategic focus. Additionally, gender diversity on the board represents the existence of female directors (Bello & Ngerebo, 2025). In this research, it will imply the percentage of women on the board, anticipating the variety of views that will lead to social and ethical ESG impacts. The subcommittee of the board that manages ESG is called the CSR/sustainability committee (Basile et al., 2025). In this research, it will be a binary variable (present/absent), assuming that this type of committee institutionalizes ESG integration, which will improve performance.

This work is based on the stakeholder theory aligning to the studies of Popov & Makeeva, 2022 and Ajepe, Agbi, & Mustapha, 2021, which is based on the assumption that companies should reconcile the interests of various stakeholders (e.g., shareholders, employees, and communities) to deliver sustainable results (Freeman et al., 2020). When applied to ESG, the stakeholder theory indicates that the characteristics of the boards, including size, composition, gender diversity, and CSR committees, make firms respond to the demands of the stakeholders. The board size should be balanced to ensure the representation of the stakeholders, independent directors should aim at the broader interests, gender diversity helps to make the decision-making inclusive, and CSR committees can align the strategies with the stakeholder

expectations, which is reflected in the ESG performance of the listed service firms in Nigeria (Freeman et al., 2020; Basile et al., 2025). The present framework places the board attributes as mechanisms to act on the stakeholder theory to fill the research gap in the comprehension of their overall role in ESG in a new market situation.

Yin and Xu (2025) investigates how board size affected ESG disputes using fresh data from Chinese listed firms between 2007 and 2022. The investigation, which used fixed effects models, reveals that more ESG disputes in China may come from larger boards. This effect is more pronounced in non-manufacturing, highly polluted, non-high-tech industries; state-owned businesses; eastern areas; and non-foreign-funded businesses. The study provides variable information, but focuses on China, a well-developed country whose economic performance and culture differ from Nigeria, leaving a geographical, which is addressed in this paper in the context of Nigeria.

Ding et al. (2024) studied the impact of board characteristics on the ESG responsibilities of listed companies in Chinese listings. Utilizing panel data from 1931 A-share listed companies between 2009 and 2022, the study found that the board size positively and significantly impacts ESG outcomes. The study provides a valuable insight, but conversely, a different economic outlook, leaving a period gap. This paper focuses from 2014 to 2023 to address this gap.

Between 2016 and 2021, Pinheiro et al. (2024) looked at how board composition affected ESG performance in 390 businesses in Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Mexico, and Peru. The study discovered that larger businesses positively contribute to higher ESG performance using panel data regression and fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis techniques. Although the study adds to the body of knowledge, it only covers a five-year period, leaving a period gap that the publication fills by extending it to ten years.

Itan et al. (2025) investigated the role of board composition on ESG disclosure in Indonesia. Employing panel data regression analysis of 256 observations from 64 Indonesian Stock Exchange companies over 2019-2022, the study found that board compensation demonstrates robust positive associations with ESG transparency, highlighting their critical roles in enhancing oversight capacity and aligning managerial incentives. The research contributes theoretically by challenging universal governance prescriptions and demonstrating contextual variations in board mechanism effectiveness within emerging economies, but it used a short period and geographical gaps are filled by this study, focusing on recent data and Nigerian service firms.

Collecchio et al. (2024) document the role of board composition in shaping ESG performance in European companies to analyze data of 253 listed companies selected from the ESG index between 2010 and 2019. The paper found that board independence has a significantly positive effect on the ESG. The paper contributes to the existing study, but focuses on developed nations, limiting its generalization, which is addressed by this study in focusing African context. Nuhu and Alam (2024) examined board characteristics and ESG disclosure in the energy industry in emerging economies. The paper adopts the Bloomberg ESG rating to measure the extent of ESG disclosure using a sample of 1,260 observations from BRICS

emerging economies, and using multiple regression techniques, found a relatively low (at 37%) level of ESG disclosure among the sampled firms and a relatively high degree of variability. The paper found that board composition is positively and significantly related to the level of ESG disclosure. The study is of high value, but focuses on the energy industry, leaving a sectoral gap, addressed by this paper by concentrating on services firms.

Eliwa et al. (2023) studied the relationship between board gender diversity and the ESG decoupling and the mitigating role of religiosity in the outlined relationship. Basing the study on the concept of the upper echelon theory and the gender socialization theory, using an international sample of 26,176 firm-year observations (including observations between 2005 and 2019), the researchers discovered that the more gender-diverse the board of directors, the less the ESG decoupling practices of firms. The same relationship is more pronounced between firms that are domiciled in countries with a low degree of religiosity. This paper is an addition to the debate on ESG decoupling, yet there is no mention of the country and the specific companies of coverage; hence, there are geographical gaps and sectoral gaps. Thus, these gaps are filled by looking at listed firms in the Nigerian setting.

The article by Wasiuzzaman and Subramaniam (2023) investigates the gender diversity on boards and the ES disclosure in energy companies in developed and developing countries based on the data of 48 countries in the period of 13 years (2004-2016). The researchers concluded that overall, the female directors positively affect the quality of disclosure of ESG and its separate aspects (except governance). Nevertheless, the research emphasizes the application of accounting standards in enhancing the role of female directors on corporate boards, though it is not country-specific and includes an outdated period, which creates geographical, industry, and time gaps. This is filled in this study by focusing Nigerian context, sector-specific, and covers the period from 2014 to 2024.

Kampoowale et al. (2024) investigated the relationship between board gender diversity and financial performance (FP) in the Malaysian emerging market, focusing on the mediating role of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance. Using a dataset of 976 observations from Malaysian publicly listed companies from 2016 to 2023, employing Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) with the Baron and Kenny approach and Two-Stage Least Squares (2SLS) regression for robustness, the study found that higher BGD positively and significantly impacts ESG performance. The study provides a valuable insight, but adopts SEM and Two-Stage Least Squares, leaving a methodological gap, which is filled in this study by adopting General Least Squares (GLS).

Menicucci and Paolucci (2025) investigated board characteristics and ESG performance European utilities sector, utilizing a sample of 119 listed utility companies for the period 2018–2024 and with an econometric model applying unbalanced panel data regression with firm fixed effects and controls per year; the study found that CSR/sustainability committees positively impact ESG performance. However, the study would inspire utility companies to define the internal governance mechanisms thoroughly, but not focusing on service firms, not in the Nigerian context, based on unbalanced data and the adoption of fixed effect model, leaving sectoral, geographical, methodological gaps, which this study addressed by focusing on Nigeria

context, service firms, using a balance data, and GLS. Puri and Moses (2023) investigated board characteristics and ESG in New Zealand-listed companies. The study sample included quarterly data from 2010 to 2021, found that CSR/sustainability committees have a significant positive impact on the ESG performance of companies. The study significantly contributes to the existing literature by providing valuable insights, but it limited its findings to New Zealand, leaving a geographical gap, which this study addressed in the context of Nigeria.

Jamil and Wahyuni (2025) investigated the impact of audit committee effectiveness and the environmental, social, and governance (ESG) rating for publicly listed firms in Malaysia, utilizing a sample of 237 listed companies for the year 2023 that disclose ESG ratings based on the FTSE Russel rating model. They found a significant positive effect of AC effectiveness on ESG rating for the firms in Malaysia. However, the study deepened the understanding of the functions of AC beyond the traditional and compulsory roles to oversee the financial reporting process, but limit generalization as the study focuses Malaysian firms, creating a geographical gap addressed in this study in the context of Nigeria. Olteanu, (2024) examined corporate governance, ESG, audit committee, and financial performance in European investment holding companies, utilizing a sample of 13 member states of the European Union from 2018 to 2020. The results show a significant positive effect of the audit committee on ESG performance. The study provides a valuable insight, but focuses European Union and covers 3 years, leaving geographical and period gaps, which are addressed in this study with a focus on the Nigerian context and extending the period to 10 years.

De Almeida and Paiva (2022) investigated audit committees and their effect on environmental, social, and governance disclosure. The study reveals a positive association between audit committees and the quality of voluntary ESG reporting, which results in greater comprehensiveness and relevance. These findings extend the academic debate, but, lack of methodological gap is addressed in this study.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research adopts an ex-post facto research design to conduct this study as the utilization is not specifically met it. The population of the study consists of 45 services firms listed on the NGX as at the end of 2013, and that remained listed at the end of 2023. The sample size of 16 was selected; this size was arrived at after filtering the firms that were not listed before end of 2013 and those without complete annual reports and accounts. The data for the study were gathered from the annual reports of the sampled service firms. The data gathered from these annual reports include ESG disclosure, board size, composition, gender diversity, CSR/sustainability committee, audit committee, and firm age (control variable). This study further adapts the model of Nuhu and Alam (2023) as:

$$ESG_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BC_{it} + \beta_3 BGD_{it} + \beta_4 BD_{it} + \epsilon$$

ESG = Environmental, Social, and Governance; BS = Board size; BC = board composition;

BGD = Board gender diversity; and BD = Board diligence

Modify as

$$ESG_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 BSZ_{it} + \beta_2 BCP_{it} + \beta_3 BGD_{it} + \beta_4 BSR_{it} + \beta_5 BAC_{it} + \beta_6 FAG_{it} + \varepsilon$$

Where:

ESG = Environmental, Social, and Governance Scores; BSZ = Board size; BCP = board composition; BGD = Board gender diversity; BSR = Board Corporate Social Responsibility/sustainability committee; BAC – Board Audit Committee; FAG= Firm Age; β_0 = Intercept; it = firm and time; and ε = error term.

For the purpose of variable measurement, the dependent variable of ESG scores is measured based on ESG dimensions of emission; environmental innovations; resource usefulness; community; human right; product responsibility; work force; management and shareholders. The ESG scores is measured based of number disclosed by a company divided by expected number to be disclosed which 9 is. The following table presents the variables used in the model above and their measurements.

Table 1: Variable measurement

Variable		Measurement	Source
Dependent variable			
ESG Scores/indexes	ESG	Obtaining the scores by indicating 1-9 for ESG disclosures or 0 for non-disclosure.	Yin and Xu (2025)
Independent Variables			
Board Size	BDZ	Absolute value number of the board	Ding et al. (2024)
Board Composition	BCP	Percentage of non-executive/ independent directors to the total no. of directors on the board	Nuhu and Alam (2023)
Board Gender diversity	BGD	Percentage of Female directors on the total no. of directors on the board.	Itan et al. (2025)
CSR Committee	BSR	Dummy variable equal to when the company has committee, otherwise it is 0,	Puri and Moses (2023)
Audit Committee	BAC	Percentage of directors in the audit committee over the total no. of directors on the board	Olteanu (2024)
Firm Age	FAG	Absolute number of years since incorporation	Olteanu (2024)

Source: Study Observation (2025)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Esg	160	.384	.142	0	.6
Bsz	160	10.125	1.977	7	14
Bcp	160	.675	.123	.38	.9
Bgd	160	.181	.14	0	.57
Bsr	160	.35	.478	0	1
Bac	160	.607	.149	0	1.2
Fag	160	6.817	.648	4.77	7.9

Source: STATA 13, 2025

Table 2 present descriptive statistics results, indicate that the mean of the ESG performance (0.384) value is relatively to, demonstrating a moderately fair level of environmental, social, and governance disclosure of the sampled firms. The board size on average is around 10 directors, indicating observation of a recommendation given by the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance of 5 to 15 board members. The composition of the board, in terms of the percentage of independent or non-executive directors, is 0.675, and this indicates a rather balanced board structure. The average gender diversity in boards (0.181) also suggests that women take approximately 18 percent of board positions, which is a sign of low differences in women in the Nigerian listed companies. The variable CSR/sustainability committee has a mean of 0.35, as only 35% of the firms are characterized by the presence of a specific sustainability committee. The mean of the audit committee variable is 0.607 and indicates that this variable is active in the majority of companies.

Table 3: Shapiro-Francia W' test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W'	V'	z	Prob>z
esg	160	0.996	0.607	-1.019	0.846
bsz	160	0.977	3.046	2.270	0.012
bcp	160	0.989	1.541	0.881	0.189
bgd	160	0.926	9.989	4.690	0.000
bsr	160	1.000	0.000	.	0.000
bac	160	0.945	7.345	4.064	0.000
fag	160	0.961	5.241	3.376	0.000

Source: STATA 13, 2025

Table 3 indicates that among all the variables under study, only esg and bc are normally distributed as they are not significant at 5%. But other variable are significant, implying they are not normally distributed. The existence of non-normal regressors renders the use of a firm estimation method. The Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) model is therefore justified to use in the study to correct the heteroskedasticity and non-normality because it would guarantee reliable and efficient estimation of the parameters.

Table 4: Pairwise correlations

Variables	esg	Bs	bc	bgd	csrsc	ac	Fa
Esg	1.000						
Bsz	-0.060 (0.450)	1.000					
Bcp	-0.127 (0.110)	-0.126 (0.113)	1.000				
Bgd	0.055 (0.492)	0.050 (0.532)	-0.105 (0.188)	1.000			
bsr	0.368* (0.000)	0.133 (0.094)	0.309* (0.000)	-0.178* (0.025)	1.000		
bac	0.008 (0.915)	-0.021 (0.788)	0.114 (0.150)	-0.237* (0.003)	-0.117 (0.139)	1.000	
Fag	-0.075 (0.343)	-0.072 (0.365)	0.042 (0.596)	-0.582* (0.000)	-0.013 (0.872)	0.237* (0.003)	1.000

Source: STATA 13, 2025

Table 4 shows that ESG is positively related to the CSR/sustainability committee ($r = 0.368$, $p < 0.01$) and board gender diversity ($r = 0.055$, albeit not very significant), which means that the company with a special sustainability committee and a higher number of women is more likely to have a higher ESG performance. In addition, explanatory variables are not strongly correlated among themselves the coefficients are less than the threshold of 80%, indicating that there is little likelihood of multicollinearity, which is also supported by the VIF test in Table 5.

Table 5: Multicollinearity Test

	VIF	1/VIF
bgd	1.638	.611
Fag	1.563	.64
Bsr	1.244	.804
Bcp	1.171	.854
Bac	1.129	.886
Bsz	1.059	.945
Mean VIF	1.301	.
Hausma	0.859	

Source: STATA 13, 2025

Table 5 documents VIF mean of 1.301 is quite lower than the threshold of 10, and it indicates the absence of the issue of multicollinearity in the model. The Hottest (0.806) and Hausman (0.859) statistics provide a reason, which is that to provide robust and efficient estimation, it is better to use the FGLS estimator to overcome the possible heteroskedasticity and serial correlation.

Table 6: Cross-sectional FGLS regression

Esg	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	Sig
bsz	-.013	.005	-2.50	.012	**
bcp	-.36	.085	-4.23	.000	***
bgd	.152	.088	1.72	.085	*
bsr	.158	.023	6.98	.000	***
bac	.136	.069	1.96	.051	*
fag	-.003	.019	-0.17	.866	
Constant	.612	.162	3.78	.000	***
Number of obs	160		Chi-square		54.987
Prob > chi2	0.000				

Source: STATA 13, 2025

Table 6 shows the outcome of the cross-sectional time series FGLS regression model. The overall Wald Chi2 of 54.987, and a p value < 0.001 , indicates that it is significant, i.e., variations in ESG performance are jointly explained by the board attributes.

The H_{01} , which provides that the size of boards does not have any significant effect on ESG, is rejected since the coefficient has a negative and significant value (p value = 0.012). This suggests that larger boards are more likely to affect ESG performance negatively among the service firms in Nigeria, which conforms to the position of Yin and Xu (2025) that larger boards would be affected by coordination challenges that would result in inefficiency in dealing with

stakeholder concerns. This observation is in line with the stakeholder theory, which shows that an optimal board size is required to achieve a balance between effective decision-making and a representative sample of the stakeholders (Freeman et al., 2020).

H₀₂ is also not accepted because the relationship between board composition and ESG is significantly negative ($p = 0.000$). Such an outcome could indicate the superiority of executive directors or the formal independence of non-executive directors in the Nigerian setting, which restrained their ability to pursue the stakeholder interests using ESG policies. Just like the findings of Nuhu and Alam (2024) and Collevicchio et al. (2024), the context-specificity of board composition impacts ESG in both positive and negative ways; thus, it is not enough to appoint independent directors unless an individual makes them active participants in sustainability control.

H₀₃ indicates that board gender diversity has a positive yet the insignificant impact on ESG (p value = 0.085), and hence accept the null hypothesis. It means that gender-diverse boards are more likely to deliver better ESG results, which is in line with Eliwa et al. (2023) and Kampoowale et al. (2024), who found that women directors increase ethical sensitivity and transparency. The insignificance could, however, be due to the fact that the percentage of women in Nigerian boards (mean = 0.181) is very small, and hence they have little power to influence sustainability decisions.

The null hypothesis (H₀₄), which states that the CSR/sustainability committee does not significantly impact the ESG, is decisively disapproved. The strongly significant and positive coefficient (p value = 0.000) indicates that companies articulated in the presence of the CSR or sustainability committees have high performance in terms of ESG. This is in keeping with stakeholder theory, since these committees institutionalize the stakeholder engagement directly, making a link between corporate governance and sustainability (Menicucci & Paolucci, 2025; Puri & Moses, 2023). The implication of the finding is that dedicated board structures contribute greatly to the ESG alignment with stakeholder expectations within service firms in Nigeria.

H₀₅, that the audit committee does not have significant impact on ESG, is rejected at a 10 percent level by an insignificant margin ($p = 0.051$). This good relationship indicates that the audit committee is an important institution in enhancing the quality and compliance of ESG reporting. The finding supports the conclusions made by Jamil and Wahyuni (2025) and De Almeida and Paiva (2022), who reported that an audit committee is positively related to the quality of ESG disclosures. This finding supports the stakeholder theory, as it demonstrates that an effective audit committee improves accountability and transparency in the ESG performance

5. CONCLUSION

The strong conviction of the research is that board qualities are crucial factors that influence the ESG performance of the listed service companies in Nigeria because good governance systems, board diversity, and proper sustainability control mechanisms increase the sensitivity

of the firms to the demands of the stakeholders and their long-term sustainability. The research finds that the large and unbalanced boards are likely to undermine the ESG performance, whereas gender diversity, CSR/sustainability committees, and audit committees enhance the sustainability integration and transparency at a significant level. This study is based on the principles of the stakeholder theory and confirms that the balanced board mechanisms can be considered as the necessary tools to align the work of a specific company with the priorities of society and the environment, as well as enhance the overall ESG profile of the service firms in Nigeria.

5.1 Recommendations

- 1) Companies should have an ideal size of the board that would help in making decisions and coordinating them.
- 2) Company should follow the inclusion of independent, competent, and professionally skilled directors on the board to facilitate objectivity and sustainability focus.
- 3) Firms should have more female representation on the boards to become more inclusive and refine the outcome of the decisions regarding ESG.
- 4) Listed service companies should form a CSR/sustainability committee whose mandate is to formulate and manage ESG plans.
- 5) The firm audit committees should extend their scrutinizing to encompass the assurance of the sustainability reporting and ESG risk management.

Declaration

All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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Notes:
1. (/v# option or -set maxvar-) 5000 maximum variables

```

```

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```

```
. xtset id year, yearly
      panel variable: id (strongly balanced)
      time variable: year, 2014 to 2023
      delta: 1 year
```

```
. sum esg bs bc bgd csrsc ac fa
```

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
esg	160	.384375	.1421076	0	.6
bs	160	10.125	1.97707	7	14
bc	160	.6746875	.1233593	.38	.9
bgd	160	.1806875	.1404849	0	.57
csrsc	160	.35	.4784672	0	1
ac	160	.6065625	.1486038	0	1.2
fa	160	6.816813	.6483946	4.77	7.9

```
. sfrancia esg bs bc bgd csrsc ac fa
```

Shapiro-Francia W' test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W'	V'	z	Prob>z
esg	160	0.99550	0.607	-1.019	0.84578
bs	160	0.97739	3.046	2.270	0.01162
bc	160	0.98856	1.541	0.881	0.18920
bgd	160	0.92585	9.989	4.690	0.00001
csrsc	160	1.00000	-0.000	.	0.00001
ac	160	0.94547	7.345	4.064	0.00002
fa	160	0.96110	5.241	3.376	0.00037

```
. pwcorr esg bs bc bgd csrsc ac fa, sig star(5)
```

	esg	bs	bc	bgd	csrsc	ac	fa
esg	1.0000						
bs	-0.0602 0.4498	1.0000					
bc	-0.1267 0.1102	-0.1257 0.1133	1.0000				
bgd	0.0547 0.4919	0.0497 0.5323	-0.1047 0.1876	1.0000			
csrsc	0.3677* 0.0000	0.1330 0.0937	0.3087* 0.0001	-0.1776* 0.0246	1.0000		
ac	0.0085 0.9154	-0.0214 0.7879	0.1144 0.1496	-0.2366* 0.0026	-0.1174 0.1392	1.0000	
fa	-0.0755 0.3427	-0.0721 0.3652	0.0423 0.5957	-0.5819* 0.0000	-0.0128 0.8724	0.2372* 0.0025	1.0000

```
. reg esg bs bc bgd csrsc ac fa
```

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs =	160
Model	.82125887	6	.136876478	F(6, 153) =	8.76
Residual	2.38967883	153	.015618816	Prob > F	= 0.0000
Total	3.2109377	159	.020194577	R-squared	= 0.2558
				Adj R-squared	= 0.2266
				Root MSE	= .12498

esg	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
bs	-.0126119	.0051581	-2.45	0.016	-.0228021 -.0024217
bc	-.3600137	.0869592	-4.14	0.000	-.5318095 -.188218
bgd	.1518895	.0902878	1.68	0.095	-.0264823 .3302613
csrsc	.1576001	.0231023	6.82	0.000	.1119594 .2032407
ac	.1355116	.0708704	1.91	0.058	-.0044992 .2755225
fa	-.003149	.0191122	-0.16	0.869	-.040907 .034609
_cons	.6116322	.165334	3.70	0.000	.285 .9382644

```
. hettest
```

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance

Variables: fitted values of esg

chi2(1) = 0.06

Prob > chi2 = 0.8061

```
. vif
```

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
bgd	1.64	0.610567
fa	1.56	0.639659
csrsc	1.24	0.803964
bc	1.17	0.853643
ac	1.13	0.885649
bs	1.06	0.944572
Mean VIF	1.30	

. xtreg esg bs bc bgd csrsc ac fa, fe

```
Fixed-effects (within) regression      Number of obs   =   160
Group variable: id                    Number of groups =   16

R-sq:  within = 0.2218                Obs per group: min =   10
      between = 0.0662                avg           =  10.0
      overall  = 0.0752                max           =   10

corr(u_i, Xb) = -0.2057                F(6,138)       =   6.56
                                          Prob > F        =   0.0000
```

esg	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
bs	-.0009828	.0021167	-0.46	0.643	-.0051682	.0032026
bc	-.0902355	.0771998	-1.17	0.244	-.2428829	.0624119
bgd	-.0044008	.0499163	-0.09	0.930	-.1031005	.0942989
csrsc	.113957	.0282738	4.03	0.000	.0580511	.1698629
ac	-.0761097	.0324992	-2.34	0.021	-.1403705	-.0118488
fa	.0641723	.0221427	2.90	0.004	.0203896	.1079551
_cons	.0248316	.1698937	0.15	0.884	-.3110998	.3607631
sigma_u	.13888429					
sigma_e	.0379207					
rho	.93062228	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

F test that all u_i=0: F(15, 138) = 101.59 Prob > F = 0.0000

. est store fe

. xtreg esg bs bc bgd csrsc ac fa, re

```
Random-effects GLS regression      Number of obs   =   160
Group variable: id                 Number of groups =   16

R-sq:  within = 0.2204                Obs per group: min =   10
      between = 0.0873                avg           =  10.0
      overall  = 0.0958                max           =   10

corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)           Wald chi2(6)    =   40.45
                                          Prob > chi2     =   0.0000
```

esg	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
bs	-.0013215	.0020841	-0.63	0.526	-.0054062	.0027633
bc	-.1070229	.0747325	-1.43	0.152	-.2534959	.0394501
bgd	.0048431	.0489371	0.10	0.921	-.0910718	.100758
csrsc	.1172102	.0263054	4.46	0.000	.0656526	.1687678
ac	-.075412	.0316005	-2.39	0.017	-.1373477	-.0134762
fa	.0542437	.0204684	2.65	0.008	.0141265	.094361
_cons	.1040359	.1622124	0.64	0.521	-.2138946	.4219665
sigma_u	.14658055					
sigma_e	.0379207					
rho	.93727141	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

. est store re

. hausman fe re

	Coefficients		(b-B) Difference	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B)) S.E.
	(b) fe	(B) re		
bs	-.0009828	-.0013215	.0003386	.0003701
bc	-.0902355	-.1070229	.0167874	.0193613
bgd	-.0044008	.0048431	-.0092439	.0098387
csrsc	.113957	.1172102	-.0032532	.0103651
ac	-.0761097	-.075412	-.0006977	.0075901
fa	.0641723	.0542437	.0099286	.0084465

b = consistent under Ho and Ha; obtained from xtreg
B = inconsistent under Ha, efficient under Ho; obtained from xtreg

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

chi2(6) = (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B)^(-1)](b-B)
= 2.58
Prob>chi2 = 0.8594

. xttest0

Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects

esg[id,t] = Xb + u[id] + e[id,t]

Estimated results:

	Var	sd = sqrt(Var)
esg	.0201946	.1421076
e	.001438	.0379207
u	.0214859	.1465805

Test: Var(u) = 0

chibar2(01) = 519.98
Prob > chibar2 = 0.0000

. xtgls esg bs bc bgd csrsc ac fa, panel (iid) corr (independent)

Cross-sectional time-series FGLS regression

Coefficients: generalized least squares
Panels: homoskedastic
Correlation: no autocorrelation

Estimated covariances = 1 Number of obs = 160
Estimated autocorrelations = 0 Number of groups = 16
Estimated coefficients = 7 Time periods = 10
Wald chi2(6) = 54.99
Log likelihood = 109.291 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000

esg	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
bs	-.0126119	.005044	-2.50	0.012	-.0224978 -.0027259
bc	-.3600137	.0850357	-4.23	0.000	-.5266806 -.1933468
bgd	.1518895	.0882907	1.72	0.085	-.0211571 .3249361
csrsc	.1576001	.0225913	6.98	0.000	.113322 .2018782
ac	.1355116	.0693028	1.96	0.051	-.0003193 .2713425
fa	-.003149	.0186895	-0.17	0.866	-.0397797 .0334817
_cons	.6116322	.1616768	3.78	0.000	.2947514 .928513